

Sample 10a

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0060
	{Fe}	20.5
	{Ca}	15.0
	{S, Ca}	9.0
	{Si}	8.0
	{Al, Ca}	7.7
	{Si, Ca HiP}	6.9
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.7
	{Ca, Fe}	3.4
	{Al, Si}	3.0
	{Si, S, Ca}	2.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.5
	{Cl}	1.1
	{Mg, Fe}	1.1
	{Si, Fe}	1.0
	{Mg, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.8
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg, Si}	0.7
	{Na, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Mg}	0.6
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.6
	{Na, Si}	0.5
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Zn-LA1}	0.5
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.5
	{Cl}	0.4
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.4
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.4
	{Al, Si, K}	0.4
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Na, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Si, S, Ca}	0.3

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	20.6
Pellet	2.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	12.6
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.2
Ore / hot metal	0.6
BOF converter slag	16.3
BOF converter slag slopping	2.4
Slag BOF converter or desulph	5.3
Desulph slag	1.5
Ca-aluminate slag	8.2
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.4
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	4.6
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	1.0
Fe-metal rich	0.3
Coal and cokes or soil	0.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.0
Carbon rich - other	2.5
Cement or BOF converter	0.8
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.9
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.1
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	3.6
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.1
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.1
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.2
Unassigned other	3.6

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	35.7
Site - ore / hot metal	0.6
Site - slag	39.6
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	4.6
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	1.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.3
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	0.9
Site - carbon-rich other	2.0
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	2.5
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.8
Urban	1.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	3.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	3.8

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 10b

Greyscale Image

140 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0095
{Fe}	20.8
{Ca}	16.2
{S, Ca}	9.4
{Si}	7.7
{Al, Ca}	7.6
{Si, Ca HiP}	6.5
{Si, Ca LoP}	3.7
{Ca, Fe}	3.5
{Al, Si}	2.6
{Si, S, Ca}	2.5
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.7
{Cl}	1.3
{Si, Fe}	1.1
{Mg, Fe}	0.9
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.9
{Mg, Si}	0.8
{Mg, Ca}	0.7
{Na, Si}	0.6
{Al, S, Ca}	0.6
{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.6
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.6
{Mg}	0.5
{Zn-LA1}	0.5
{Na, Si, Ca}	0.5
{S, Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Cl}	0.4
{Na, Al, Si}	0.4
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.4
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.4
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
{Al, Si, K}	0.3
{Al}	0.3
{Na, S, Ca}	0.3
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	21.7
Pellet	2.4
Ore preparation undifferentiated	11.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.2
Ore / hot metal	0.9
BOF converter slag	14.8
BOF converter slag slopping	1.6
Slag BOF converter or desulph	5.5
Desulph slag	1.6
Ca-aluminate slag	7.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.1
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.9
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	1.2
Fe-metal rich	0.2
Coal and cokes or soil	0.7
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.4
Carbon rich - other	3.6
Cement or BOF converter	1.5
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	1.1
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	3.6
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.5
Misc silicates including natural	0.2
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.1
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.2
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	3.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	35.6
Site - ore / hot metal	0.9
Site - slag	30.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	3.9
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	1.2
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	0.7
Site - carbon-rich other	3.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	3.6
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.5
Urban	1.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	3.6
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.5
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.2
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	3.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 10c

Greyscale Image

140 μm

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0191
{Fe}	24.6
{Ca}	13.7
{S, Ca}	8.4
{Si}	7.5
{Al, Ca}	7.2
{Si, Ca HiP}	6.3
{Ca, Fe}	3.7
{Si, Ca LoP}	3.2
{Si, S, Ca}	2.6
{Al, Si}	2.5
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.3
{Cl}	1.2
{Si, Fe}	1.1
{Mg, Fe}	1.0
{Al, Si, K}	1.0
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.8
{Mg, Ca}	0.8
{Mg}	0.7
{Al, S, Ca}	0.6
{Na, Cl, Ca}	0.6
{Zn-LA1}	0.6
{Na, Si}	0.6
{S, Ca, Fe}	0.6
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.5
{Na, Si, Ca}	0.5
{Mg, Si}	0.5
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
{Na, Al, Si}	0.4
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.4
{Cl}	0.4
{Al}	0.4
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.4
{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.3
{Na, Ca}	0.3

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	22.4
Pellet	2.6
Ore preparation undifferentiated	13.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	1.6
BOF converter slag	12.3
BOF converter slag slopping	1.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	5.2
Desulph slag	0.6
Ca-aluminate slag	6.8
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.3
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.4
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	1.0
Fe-metal rich	0.2
Coal and cokes or soil	1.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.4
Carbon rich - other	3.9
Cement or BOF converter	0.9
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	1.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	2.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	9.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.2
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	3.7

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	39.0
Site - ore / hot metal	1.6
Site - slag	26.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	3.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.4
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	1.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.2
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	1.0
Site - carbon-rich other	3.4
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	3.9
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.9
Urban	1.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	2.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	9.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	3.9

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels